

Predicting the Stage of Colorectal Cancer Using Potential mRNA-Based Biomarker

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Abstract:-

Objective: To use classification machine learning techniques to differentiate between early and late-stage colorectal cancer based on individuals' mRNA profiles with clinically recorded data.

Methods: A gene signature of 14 unique mRNAs was found using a benchmark dataset extracted from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) [1]. The data of the genes were normalized using statistical methods, and the stages of the cancer were divided into the early and late stages. The best genes were found using hypothesis testing. The gene set was then tested on a new dataset gathered using the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) [2] using the GSE32323 accession number. A null hypothesis was also considered for the study.

Results: A training accuracy of 75% was achieved for the gene expression with a ROC-AUC score of 0.81 for the TCGA dataset using an ensemble technique. On this gene expression, a testing accuracy of 74% and a ROC-AUC score of 0.72 was achieved for the GEO dataset. The null hypothesis was also proven wrong in favour of the alternative hypothesis.

Conclusion: The study successfully proved the hypothesis and presented a set of 14 unique mRNAs that help predict the stage of Colorectal cancer in an individual.

Keywords:- Biomarker, Ensemble Technique, Hypothesis Testing, mRNA, Machine Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Among all the cancers known to humankind, colorectal cancer stands at the third position for death related to cancer in men and women. It is the second most common cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide when the number of men and women are combined [3]. Colonoscopy is the best possible test that is carried out to detect colorectal cancer; however, there are a few shortcomings of this test. The test is not good enough to detect small polyps and cancers. Sedation is used for the test, and it takes a long time to wear off in most cases [4]. The detection rate ranges from 7.4 to 52.5%, which is very low as, in most cases, colorectal cancer goes undetected by colonoscopy tests [5]. Colorectal cancer is a highly treatable disease that is curable when it is localized to the bowel but detecting it is the most challenging part. The primary form of treatment is surgery, resulting in a cure for approximately 50 per cent of the patients unable to get surgery which is the primary form of treatment [6]. The 5-year relative survival rate for localized colorectal cancer is 91

per cent, 72 per cent for regional colorectal cancer (Stage III) and 14 per cent for distant colorectal cancer (Stage IV). The overall survival rate stands at 64 per cent, implying that classifying the cancer stage is one of the most critical tasks [7]. A better understanding of the genetic mutations that cause CRC, the requirement for laboratory techniques to measure the resulting phenotypes and genotypes, and the attainment of regulatory qualification for clinical use are all obstacles that must be overcome before novel molecular tests can be integrated into routine clinical practice [8]. The Carcinoembryonic Antigen (CEA) makes it difficult to guess the stage of colorectal cancer since it lacks sensitivity [9].

The rapid development in technology such as Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) and many companies focusing on cancer research have led to the development of The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) and International Cancer Genomic Consortium (ICGC). There is a considerable amount of genomics, epigenomics, and transcriptomics data available for different types of cancer, which have helped immensely in the study of cancer diagnosis and prognosis. TCGA data is available in four levels: 1 – raw, 2 – processed, 3 – interpreted, and 4 – summarised, which allows for studying genomics at different levels [10].

Machine Learning has become an instrumental part of medical sciences and is applied across various cancer for diagnosis and prognosis. One can apply different machine learning techniques to predict a patient's cancer stage using the transcriptomic features. In this study, we have focused on classifying early (t1 & t2) and late (t3 & t4) samples of colorectal cancer. In the past, gene markers and other patient features have been used along with Machine Learning techniques such as random forest, general linear model, and neural network for clinically relevant outcomes. The researchers achieved an accuracy of 0.71 on blind test data [11]. For risk prediction and stratification of colorectal cancer, a set of classification machine learning was applied and achieved a concordance of 0.70 ± 0.02 , sensitivity of 0.63 ± 0.06 , and specificity of 0.82 ± 0.04 [12]. Another study was conducted where five machine learning methods – Logistic Regression, k-Nearest Neighbors, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest and Naïve Bayes, were applied. They achieved the highest AUC of 0.865, sensitivity of 0.895, specificity of 0.835, PPV of 84.4 and NPV of 88.9% for Logistic Regression [13].

In the paper by Chan et al., the authors have determined a gene signature using the gene expression data, which can identify the high risk of recurrence among stage 1 and stage 2 patients of colorectal cancer. They used three methods, namely - significance analysis of microarrays. Logistic regression and recursive feature elimination identify the genes differentially expressed among the patients with and without recurrence. They also used bagging and Support Vector Machines in the prediction model of training data. In training data, they achieved a sensitivity of 91.18%, whereas, in the validation dataset, 80% and 91.67% were obtained in two countries [14].

Hammad et al. aimed to determine the potential biomarkers for Colorectal Cancer. They performed machine learning analysis and integrated bioinformatics to determine the biomarkers for its prognosis. The authors acquired the gene expression microarray data from this study's Gene Expression Omnibus database. Consequently, they identified the differentially expressed genes and functionally analyzed them via Kyoto Enrichment of Genes, Genomes, and Gene Ontology. Protein-protein interaction network was also investigated, and a Support Vector Machine was used on training data. They focussed on the AUC-ROC metric, for which they obtained a ROC-AUC of 98% in training data and 96% in testing data [15].

Wan et al. determined a cell-free DNA (cfDNA) gene signature that can potentially reflect tumour and non-tumour contributions for early cancer detection. They performed whole-genome sequencing on cfDNA and extracted the reads aligning to protein-coding gene bodies, followed by normalization of the read counts. Machine learning models were trained to assess generalization performance using k-fold cross-validation and confounder-based cross-validations. They achieved a mean AUC of 0.92 (95% CI 0.91–0.93) with a mean sensitivity of 85% (95% CI 83–86%) at 85% specificity in a colorectal cancer cohort which was heavily weighted towards early-stage cancer (80% stage I/II). The machine learning model achieved high sensitivity and specificity in a large, predominantly early-stage colorectal cancer cohort [16].

The major drawback of these studies was that they did not focus on finding an mRNA gene signature which would help create a strong foundation for predicting the stage of colorectal cancer. And a few studies which did focus on finding a gene signature it was based on miRNA. Since mRNA plays a vital role in diagnosis and prognosis, we cannot ignore them from our study; hence they are necessary while evaluating the stage of colorectal cancer. In this study, we try to predict the stage using data from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA). We tried to find a gene signature which was the most prevalent in classifying the stage of colorectal cancer.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

The dataset used in this study is the benchmark dataset available on The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA), which consists of around 33,000 mRNA. The data is presented as reads per million mRNA mapped (rpmm). Two datasets were downloaded for this study: expression data and clinical data. The datasets were merged using the barcode reader column named `patient.bcr_patient_barcode`, and the pathologic stage was also included in the combined dataset. From the new dataset, the sample for whom the stage of the cancer was not recorded was dropped. The pathological stage of the patients was labelled as - 'stage i', 'stage ia', 'stage ii', 'stage iia', 'stage iib', 'stage iic', 'stage iii', 'stage iiia', 'stage iiib', 'stage iiic', 'stage iv', 'stage iva' and 'stage ivb'. The stages ranging from i to iic were combined with the early stage, and the other stages were combined with the late stage. This changes our problem from a multiclass problem to a binary classification problem.

A testing dataset was extracted from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) using the GEOparse library [17]. The dataset used for testing had the accession number GSE32323 and consisted of 54675 mRNAs and 44 samples. The dataset consisted of 10 samples that did not have a record for the cancer stage, and those records were dropped. The dataset initially consisted of pathological stages labelled 1, 2a, 2b, 3a, 3b and 4. The next step was to categorize these stages into early and late stages to match the values in the target column of the training dataset. The number of early and late-stage samples was checked for the testing data and was found to be spread even for both categories. The count is shown below in figure 1.

Fig 1. Count of samples in early and late stage

B. Data Pre-processing

After cleaning the data, the first step was to normalize the data. This is done because the values for mRNA can range from decimals to hundreds making the data scattered over a vast scale, which can affect the performance of a machine learning model. We added one to the value to ensure the model avoids $\log(0)$ errors. The data was then log-transformed to bring the information on a uniform scale followed by quantile normalization. Quantile normalization makes two distributions identical in statistical properties. The

final pre-processing step was standard scaling, also known as the z-score transformation, which makes the mean expression 0 for all samples. The testing dataset was normalized using the standard scaling, also known as the z-score transformation.

C. Feature Selection

With just pertinent data and eliminating irrelevant data, feature selection is a technique for lowering the input variable for the model [18]. To find such features, which refer to genes, we have used a few different statistical methods using Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis (WEKA) [19]. Select K-Best, Random Forest, Correlation, CfsSubsetEval + BestFirst, CfsSubsetEval + Greedy, CorrelationAttributeEval + Ranker, ReliefAttributeEval +

Ranker, and ClassifierAttributeEval + Ranker were the methods used to find the genes that had maximum correlation with the target column, Stage. The genes with the highest occurrence amongst all the methods mentioned above were selected as the most important features for predicting the stage of Colorectal Cancer. The selected genes consisted of - LEMD2, ACADSB, ARHGEF7, CDCA2, CARKD, CNOT7, EFNB2, FBXO25, PLAG1, SAMM50, GSR, KBTBD2, PALM3, and WIPI2. Boxplot is a plot that helps graphically display a variable's location and spread. It also indicates the data's symmetry and skewness and displays the outliers. This plot helped us understand the data spread for the selected genes and compare them with each other [20]. The box plot of the selected genes is shown below in figure 2.

Fig 2. Boxplots of the selected genes

The entire pipeline to evaluate the stage prediction is depicted in figure 3 below.

Fig 3. Pipeline for Stage Prediction

D. Machine Learning Techniques

In many bioinformatics studies and applications, machine learning is applied. Machine learning techniques have been used in various fields, including pattern recognition, which has led to accumulated knowledge about the right and ethical ways to apply them [21]. The algorithms used in this research are - Logistic Regression, Artificial Neural Network, Gaussian Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbors, AdaBoost, XGBoost, and Gradient Boosting.

➤ Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is an algorithm that best suits categorical data. The model changes the probability of a sample belonging to a class in the form of yes/no or 0/1. It uses a sigmoidal function to calculate the probability of belonging to a particular category [22].

➤ Artificial Neural Networks

Artificial neural networks (ANN) are made of multi-layer, fully-connected neural nets. An input layer, several hidden layers, and an output layer constitute them. Each node

in one layer is linked to each node in the layer above it. By adding more hidden layers, we make the network deeper. A specific node runs a nonlinear activation function on the weighted sum of its inputs. This is the node's output, which later serves as the input for a different node in the following layer. This process is carried out for each node, and the outcome—the signal flowing from left to right—is determined [23].

➤ Gaussian Naïve Bayes

Gaussian Naïve Bayes is a particular type of Naïve Bayes algorithm. When the features contain continuous values, it is specially employed. It is presumptive that all features follow a normal or gaussian distribution [24].

➤ Random Forest

Many decision trees are built during the random forests' training phase, or the random decision forests ensemble learning approach, which is used for classification, regression, and other tasks. Most of the trees chosen class is the random forest's output for classification problems [25].

➤ *Support Vector Machine*

SVM is an algorithm used for classification. SVM works on finding the best suitable hyperplane in an N-dimensional space to classify data points distinctly. Hyperplanes are decision boundaries. Points closer to the hyperplane are Support Vectors, and they influence the hyperplane's position and orientation [26].

➤ *K-Nearest Neighbors*

K-Nearest Neighbors is a classifier algorithm that works on the principle of how similar one data is to another. The algorithm calculates the distance between the data points for classification and does not compare the unseen data with the other data. Different methods like Euclidian, Manhattan, and Jacquard measure the points' distance [27].

➤ *Adaptive Boost*

AdaBoost is a meta-estimator that fits a classifier on the initial dataset, followed by fitting additional copies of the classifier on the dataset with the weights of instances that were mistakenly identified being changed such that future classifiers concentrate more on difficult situations [28].

➤ *XGBoost*

XGBoost is how the gradient-boosted trees algorithm is implemented. It is a supervised learning technique that combines the predictions of some weaker, simpler models to forecast a target variable accurately [29].

E. Performance Evaluation

The performance of the chosen classifiers was evaluated using many metrics to show the results. Cross-validation of 5 folds has been performed to evaluate the classifiers. Metrics used for evaluation are:

➤ *Accuracy*

It indicates the proportion of our predictions that were accurately made based on the dataset.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (1)$$

➤ *Sensitivity*

It is also known as the true positive rate (TPR). It is expressed as a ratio that allows us to see how many positive instances the model identified correctly.

$$Sensitivity (TPR) = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (2)$$

➤ *Specificity*

It is also known as the true negative rate (TNR). It is expressed as a ratio that allows the model to see how many negative instances are correctly identified.

$$Specificity (TNR) = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \quad (3)$$

➤ *Precision*

It is also known as positive predictive value. It entails dividing the total number of accurate positive forecasts by the number of real positives (i.e., the number of true positives plus the number of false positives).

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (4)$$

➤ *Receiver Operating Characteristics (Area Under Curve) Score (ROC-AUC)*

It is a graph that displays a classification model's performance across all categorization levels. Two parameters are plotted on this curve: True Positive Rate and True Negative Rate.

➤ *F1-Score*

It refers to the harmonic mean of precision and sensitivity (Recall).

$$F1Score = 2X \left(\frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \right) \quad (5)$$

➤ *Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)*

If the prediction performed well across all four categories of the confusion matrix (true positives, false negatives, true negatives, and false positives), proportional to the number of positive items and the size of negative elements in the dataset, it produces a high score.

$$MCC = \frac{(TP \times TN) - (FP \times FN)}{\sqrt{(TP+FP)(TP+FN)(TN+FP)(TN+FN)}} \quad (6)$$

F. Packages and Tools

The complete data analysis and prediction pipeline were coded in Python 3.11.0b4 and Python 3.11.0b5 using the 'scikit-learn' (sklearn) library [30]. The Python library used for loading the data was 'pandas', and the libraries for pre-processing included 'numpy', 'scipy' and 'qnorm'. The data was visualized using 'seaborn' and 'matplotlib' libraries. The feature selection was made using Python and Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis (WEKA) [19].

III. RESULTS

A. Feature Extraction

A total of 14 features were selected using feature extraction methods, as mentioned in Feature Selection. The features selected using these methods are mentioned along with their count in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Important features and their Counts using different methods

Feature (m-RNA)	Count
LEMD2	6
ARHGEF7	4
CDCA2	4
PLAG1	4
SAMM50	4
ACADSB	3
CARKD	3
CNOT7	3
EFNB2	3
FBXO25	3
GSR	3
KBTBD2	3
PALM3	3
WIPI2	3

B. Single Gene Models

We chose the best 14 features (mRNAs) according to the features having the highest count and evaluated the AUC and accuracy of training data. We checked the performance using Logistic Regression. Each performs in the range – Accuracy (55% ~ 66%) and AUC in the range (0.61 ~ 0.81) on training data, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Performance of Top Scoring Features using Logistic Regression

Feature (m-RNA)	Training Accuracy	Training AUC
LEMD2	64%	0.65
ARHGEF7	61%	0.71
CDCA2	55%	0.63
PLAG1	66%	0.7
SAMM50	59%	0.75
ACADSB	66%	0.8
CARKD	66%	0.68
CNOT7	59%	0.67
EFNB2	66%	0.61
FBXO25	55%	0.68
GSR	66%	0.79
KBTBD2	61%	0.74
PALM3	66%	0.73
WIPI2	64%	0.81

The performance of the genes was also evaluated for the testing dataset using Logistic Regression. Each performs in the range – Accuracy (5%6 ~ 65%) and AUC in the range (0.48 ~ 0.69) on training data, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Performance of Top Scoring Features using Logistic Regression

Feature (m-RNA)	Accuracy	AUC
LEMD2	65%	0.6
ARHGEF7	56%	0.57
CDCA2	56%	0.64
PLAG1	65%	0.67
SAMM50	56%	0.48
ACADSB	56%	0.69
CARKD	62%	0.65
CNOT7	62%	0.6
EFNB2	59%	0.59
FBXO25	56%	0.65
GSR	59%	0.55
KBTBD2	62%	0.59
PALM3	56%	0.56
WIPI2	56%	0.47

The performance of the Logistic Regression model was not good for the testing dataset when compared with the training dataset performance.

C. Multiple Gene Models

Based on the single feature, we obtained the best AUC and an accuracy of 0.8 and 66% on the training dataset with ACADSB. The models' performance was improved using features selected by various feature selection methods, as mentioned in the previous section, were used as a combination. This resulted in a unique 14 mRNAs signature. Nine different machine learning techniques were implemented to develop prediction models. The training data was cross-validated five times. The results are presented in table 4 below.

Table 4: Performance Metrics for TCGA Cohort for Features collected

Algorithm	Accuracy	ROC-AUC	Cross-Validation Score	Precision	F1 Score	MCC
Gaussian Naïve Bayes	70%	0.85	0.71	0.71	0.7	0.41
Logistic Regression	73%	0.8	0.69	0.7	0.63	0.48
Random Forest	69%	0.81	0.67	0.67	0.58	0.38
SVM	78%	0.79	0.67	0.73	0.48	0.58
KNN	69%	0.75	0.62	0.66	0.63	0.38
Neural Network	75%	0.8	0.69	0.71	0.61	0.51
Gradient Boosting	67%	0.77	0.64	0.66	0.64	0.34
AdaBoost	58%	0.65	0.6	0.58	0.18	0.15
XGBoost	66%	0.73	0.64	0.65	0.59	0.31

The artificial neural network model performed best on the 14 mRNAs signature. An accuracy of 75% was achieved with a cross-validation score of 0.69. The models did not have a good cross-validation score individually, meaning the models would be unable to perform well on unseen data. The reason for such performance is over-fitting. This is known as overfitting when a machine learning model tries to include all the data points or more that are present in the given dataset. As a result, the model begins to cache erroneous values and noise from the dataset, which lowers the model's efficiency

and accuracy [31]. We use an ensemble technique known as Stacking Classifier to overcome this issue. In the stacking classifier, algorithms which are weak learners on their own are combined to form base learners. On these learners, a final learner is masked as the final layer of deciding the class [32]. We used the machine learning techniques mentioned above as the base learners and Logistic Regression as the last layer.

The next step was to validate the model's performance on a dataset that the model had not seen before. The dataset

extracted was pre-processed, as explained in the Data Pre-processing section. The results achieved for each of the

machine learning algorithms separately are shown below in table 5.

Table 5: Performance Metrics for GSE323323 Cohort for Features collected

Algorithm	Accuracy	ROC-AUC	Precision	F1-Score	MCC
Gaussian Naïve Bayes	65%	0.7	0.67	0.5	0.29
Logistic Regression	53%	0.7	0.54	0.38	0.04
Random Forest	62%	0.63	0.61	0.38	0.23
SVM	62%	0.65	0.61	0.32	0.23
KNN	53%	0.59	0.54	0.38	0.04
Neural Network	65%	0.73	0.62	0.38	0.3
Gradient Boosting	56%	0.65	0.58	0.46	0.11
AdaBoost	74%	0.78	0.76	0.12	0.47
XGBoost	53%	0.56	0.55	0.43	0.04

The AdaBoost model performed best on the 14 mRNAs signature. An accuracy of 74% was achieved with a ROC-AUC score of 0.78. A final comparison of the model's performance on the training and testing dataset was made. For this, the Stacking Classifier was only used, and accuracy and ROC-AUC score were used to evaluate the performance. The comparison is shown below in table 6.

Table 6: Performance Metrics of Stacking Classifier for Features collected

Algorithm	Accuracy	ROC-AUC
TCGA Dataset	75%	0.81
GSE323323 Dataset	74%	0.72

As can be inferred from table 6, the genes found using the training dataset had an accuracy almost equal to the testing dataset's accuracy.

D. Hypothesis Testing

The NULL hypothesis H_0 – The genes selected using the training data are neither up-regulated nor down-regulated.

The alternative hypothesis H_1 – The genes selected using the training data are either up-regulated or down-regulated.

Let alpha be the significance level. The significance level refers to the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is assumed to be true, concluding that the difference of means observed results from a real effect, while in reality, it is not [33]. A significance level of 0.05 was assumed. The hypothesis is drawn, and the significance level has been set. The p-Value for each gene was calculated and is shown in figure 4 below.

LEMD2 : 0.4355097364670588
 ACADSB : 0.40347571753883893
 ARHGEF7 : 0.6149580103255068
 CDCA2 : 0.14583494681677295
 CARKD : 0.1010516726116297
 CNOT7 : 0.43905166319461586
 EFN2 : 0.267655423311691
 FBX025 : 0.11719465492334577
 PLAG1 : 0.06024243313512829
 SAMM50 : 0.6355095727054877
 GSR : 0.40776488892700236
 KBTBD2 : 0.4479339977396374
 PALM3 : 0.9357037755885541
 WIPI2 : 0.7914762264477413

Fig 4. p-Value for the gene signature

As can be inferred from the figure above, the p-Value for each gene is more than 0.05, which means we can reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. Studies in previous years have proven that regulated genes play a role in inducing cancer [34].

IV. DISCUSSION & FUTURE WORK

Colorectal Cancer is a complicated disease that primarily affects adults 50 years and older. The survival rate is meagre for distant colorectal cancer but high for regional and localized cancer. Therefore, detecting it before it reaches the later stages is essential. Researchers have started focusing on mRNAs recently; therefore, we have decided to make an mRNA-based panel to distinguish between early and late-stage colorectal cancer. Using TCGA data, we applied pre-processing steps to ready the data for building classification machine learning models. Importance features were extracted using a combination of Python and WEKA-based feature selection techniques such as correlation, p-Value, random forest, and CfsSubsetEval, to name a few. We differentiated between early and late-stage samples with decent accuracy using nine machine learning techniques. For the gene signature gathered using a combination of feature selection techniques, Neural Network was the best discriminatory tool between the two groups. We achieved 74% accuracy and 0.72 ROC-AUC on the validation data.

This study focused only on finding an mRNA-based gene signature. The gene signature gathered using this study can be used in future studies to find an even more robust signature. These mRNAs can be used with lncRNA and miRNA to form a network of genes and find a gene signature that can be used to distinguish between cancer stages with more accurate results.

➤ Comparison with Other Studies

The performance of our method is superior to that published in the literature before. We have performed this given task with decent accuracy and ROC-AUC. In Gründner et al. [11], accuracies of 0.71 and 0.70 were achieved for dichotomous outcomes like relapse and RCT-R on blind data, respectively. The model performed well on validation data, but the study lacked other metrics, such as specificity and sensitivity, which helped gain more insight into the model and its actual performance.

In the study by Nartowt et al. [12], a concordance of 0.70 ± 0.02 , sensitivity of 0.63 ± 0.06 , and specificity of 0.82 ± 0.04 were achieved. This means that their model did not have cases of only false positives or only false negatives. The researchers tested their model only on a single dataset and did not cross-validate with unseen data. Their model may not work well considering real-time data, which it may have never seen before.

Li et al. [13] achieved the highest AUC of 0.865, the sensitivity of 0.895, specificity of 0.835, PPV of 84.4 and NPV of 88.9% for Logistic Regression. Although they could get excellent results, their study did not focus on mRNAs. The focus of this study was to find a gene signature that helps classify the stage of colorectal cancer.

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